

Efficient UDP Flood Detection in SDN Using Feature Optimization and Deep Learning

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ABSTRACT

SDN (Software Defined Networks) utilizes cutting-edge dynamic technology to promptly and precisely track and manage the flow of data across a network. Unlike conventional networks, SDNs' packet traffic can be readily predicted and you have more options for controlling the network quickly. In this paper, SDN is used to detect UDP flood attack in the network level. It is simpler to monitor data flow from networks, analyze the network, and identify many forms of malware, DoS, and DDoS. To properly categorize various kinds of attacks based on their attributes, Deep Learning approaches have been used. In order to identify UDP attacks, several methods have been suggested. However, there has been hardly any investigation on SDN. With the Software defining network Layer attack detection framework in mind, we present a UDP attack detection solution for SDN. The Error Scalar maxy normalization is used as a preprocessing step and once those traits are identified, the Iterative random wrapper Boruta technique is used to extract the features that are relevant to detect the attack. Finally, we use a framework for identifying attacks based on CICDDOS2019 dataset for attack detection at the software-defined network layer. Our solution is tested in a software-defined-networking (SDN) setting built in Python and the TensorflowKeras application programming interface and the findings show an accuracy of 99.8% in predicting the attack in the networks.

Index Terms— Software Defined Networking (SDN), Feature Selection, Normalization, Software Defined Network Layer Security, Deep Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Controlling the network, managing data flow, and organizing it are all areas where SDN departs from conventional networks. With a centralized software system, SDN is much easier to administer. Static in nature, traditional networks are far more difficult to set up, manage, and maintain. With SDN, the network's capabilities are standardized. As more and more data flows via LANs, it becomes increasingly difficult to manage and analyze it all while keeping the network safe¹. Because of this, SDN is preferable over traditional physical networks since it facilitates easier access to analyzing data in increments^{2, 3}. With SDN's centralized data flow structure, researchers can manage and respond to threats like DDoS, Spoofing, and jamming that affect the digital and physical infrastructures of institutions^{4, 5}. Software-Defined-Networking technologies are being used to manage and protect interconnected smart home systems and devices^{6, 7}. With SDN architecture, Quality of Service (QoS) management is simplified and improved⁸. Real-time packet inspection and software cognition are two of SDN's most popular services. The most typical use of SDN software is traffic data flow monitoring, allowing controllers to see routine operations and any unforeseen events as they occur in real time. Distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks may compromise the availability of services in software-defined networks (SDN) since they can affect the network at the application, control, and physical levels⁹. The Memcached objects and IP address spoofing were abused by the attacker and allows Memcached responses to target the resources and launched DDoS attack³⁴. During a distributed denial of service attack, legitimate users are unable to access the network's services and resources, this is achieved by sending the target an overwhelming number of requests. The controller has restrictions on how much data it can process, how much memory it can store, and how fast it can process data. Since each "Packet In" request from the data plane necessitates a significant number of controller actions, the controller's energy quickly depletes. According to AWS Shield¹⁰, a 2.3 Tbps DDoS assault was spotted in the first quarter of 2020. DDoS assaults are easy to initiate but difficult to defend. As DDoS assaults become more complex, more advanced detection methods are required for defense¹¹. Models based on study of SDN datasets are being used to control processes for services like quality of service (QoS), network security (NS), incident response (IR), and malware detection. Identifying DDoS in SDN traffic is difficult due to factors such as a lack of labeled network data, traffic that is both dynamic and varied¹²⁻¹⁵, packet similarities between benign and malicious DDoS assaults¹⁶, and switch layer masking of packets¹⁷. Several techniques, such as statistics, data mining, and machine learning, may be used to identify DDoS assaults. Automatic attack prevention utilizing machine learning methods is an exciting new possibility made possible by SDN for large,

complex, and evolving systems¹⁸. The recent rise in popularity and effectiveness of deep learning (DL) algorithms has made them a practical choice for developing attack detection systems with high accuracy and low false alarm rate.

Motivation of the Research is to detect UDP flood attacks in the SDN network architecture using the following methods,

- ❖ novel hybrids of the most popular traditional wrapper and Boruta models to isolate attack-related characteristics.
- ❖ The state-of-the-art attack detection CICDDOS2019 dataset is used to evaluate our proposed models.
- ❖ It is possible to recognize UDP flood attacks with better accuracy based on the selected features compared to its existing solutions.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a short introduction to the literature review. Our design and implementation techniques for identifying DDoS assaults are described in Section 3. In Section 4, the results and evaluation of the experiments are reported. Our results and suggestions for further study are presented in Section 5.

II. RELATED WORKS

The telecom network software industry has come a long way since 2008, when the OpenFlow protocol¹⁹ was first introduced. By decoupling the management and data layers, SDNs make centralized management easier²⁰. Because of its comprehensive nature, the SDN controller may access a wide range of data plane and network-related information. Consolidating this data using Machine-Learning technology allows SDNs to make knowledge-based choices across all of their functional areas. Some of these efforts²¹ utilized the built-in Machine Learning features of SDNs to do autonomous traffic segmentation. Network traffic prediction utilizing Deep Learning methods such as Long Short-Term Memory and Gated Recurrent Units has been successfully implemented by others²², enabling the SDN controller to deal with traffic congestion by rerouting the flow to a route with higher available capacity. OpenDaylight (ODL)²⁴, the Open Network Operating System (ONOS)²⁵, and other popular SDN architectures have all been shown to have security flaws²³. There is a risk of data tampering, interruptions in service, and unauthorized access due to security weaknesses in SDN networks. There have been reports of Snort-based NIDSs in the literature^{5,6}, these systems scan network traffic for indicators of intrusion and take corrective action, including network reconfiguration, if necessary. When dealing with encrypted

traffic, rule-based heuristic approaches like Snort have been shown to be ineffective for NIDS⁷. Articles in the literature investigate the development of NIDS in the setting of an SDN in further detail⁸. Several Machine-Learning classifiers, including Random Forest, Decision Trees, and XG-Boost, were put through rigorous testing by the authors of this research to determine which one was the most effective in spotting attacks. The trials made use of the NSL-KDD dataset, which is a data-mining dataset including various kinds of traffic labeled as safe or dangerous. Furthermore, the NSL-KDD dataset still has issues^{9,10} that prohibit it from giving a fair depiction of the networks in use today, despite its importance and breadth among IDS datasets. Another research²⁶ employed both synthetic and real-world traffic to train an unsupervised neural network based on self-organizing maps to detect traffic patterns. They also highlighted how readily applicable their approach would be in other contexts. They were able to cut down on the KDD-99 dataset's complexity by prioritizing the most vital elements. One strategy for handling threat mitigation in IoT networks is to use a software-defined-networking (SDN) controller²⁷ by installing a honeypot on a local SDN controller in order to partition off any malicious traffic. Researchers propose a whole pipeline for identifying attacks and blocking them in various contexts, such as Industrial Healthcare Systems using a software-defined-networking (SDN) controller and reinforcement learning¹⁰. While the use of Machine Learning in SDNs for the purpose of detecting and mitigating cyber attacks shows promise in this article, its potential susceptibility to adversarial attacks is not considered. ^{11,12} aimed at fooling Machine-Learning models by introducing undetectable modifications to the input data. DoS assaults can be detected with an F1-score of over 99.46% ²⁸, DDoS attacks may be detected with an F1-score of over 97.29% ²⁹, and other types of connection flooding can be recognized with an F1-score of over 99.95% ³⁰. All of these examples highlight the potential use of DL methods in detecting cyber attacks. None of them, however, takes into consideration the energy needs of a system of communication-network size. While it is true that some research has linked feature reduction to faster processing time and reduced model complexity ³⁰, no further optimization strategies that might make the models more energy-efficient and adaptive to real-world traffic dimensions are offered. ³²shows how DDoS attacks can exhaust controller resources and provides a solution to detect DDoS within the first five hundred packets of the attack traffic based on entropy variation of destination IP address. ³³an SDN-based flow detection method using the double P-value of transudative confidence machines for K-nearest neighbors' algorithm for detecting anomaly SDN flows and classify the flows. To detect binary and multiclass anomalies, RNN is used on NSL-KDD Dataset³⁵.

Our research uses deep-learning methods rather than packet inspection to guarantee that our system can recognize fraudulent information despite the additional layer of encryption done in

NIDS. Also, the CIC-DDOS 2019 dataset is benign and resembles the real - world data which has both PCAPs and CSV files so that we can accurately predict the attack data. The microservice-based architecture used by TensorflowSDN allows ML components to access the rest of the internal components in a flexible and efficient manner through established interfaces and protocols, which may be a limitation of preexisting solutions.

III. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

The whole forecasting processes are shown in Figure 1 below. Feature extraction from raw dataset files, evaluation of models, and attack modeling are all provided. We explain the procedures necessary to implement UDP attack detection in an SDN context.

Figure 1 Schematic representation of the SDNNet-Binary Classifier

a. Data source

The CIC-DDoS2019 dataset was created for use in the academic community³⁶. The dataset provides a comprehensive collection of many type of attacks, the most majority of which make use of reflection-based and exploitation-based amplification. Similar to the other CICNIDS datasets (IDS2017, IDDS2018, and DoS2017), this one shares its features with its siblings.

b. Data preprocessing

The three-stage procedure of attack data preparation is as follows. As a first step, we smooth the input data to mitigate the effect of noise. In a second step, dynamic latency is reduced by correlating the data. Third, the vector-quantization of the processed data is what's needed to fulfil the SDN layer attack detection framework's need for predictive modeling. The dataset's actual data often has several inaccuracies. The reliability of data-driven diagnostic techniques may be adversely affected by these mistakes. As a result, it is essential to first smooth the input. During the process of fitting, extreme values that depart from the norm are reduced. Let's suppose that the smoothing data has a length of N , that the subset's size is W (of $2M+1$), and that the polynomial's degree O is P . In order to acquire the smoothed information,

$$z[d] = \sum_{m=-M}^M h[m]x[d-m], d = 0,1,2, \dots, D-1, \quad (1)$$

where $y[d-m]$ is the $(d-m)^{th}$ sampling point, The m^{th} error coefficient, $h[m]$, is defined as follows, while the n th smoothed output value, $z[m]$, is denoted as follows:

$$h[m] = h[-m] = \sum_{k=0}^P b_k m^k, -M \leq m \leq M, P \leq 2M, \quad (2)$$

where b_k is the k^{th} coefficient of the polynomial defined as:

$$\mathbf{b} = (b_0, b_1, \dots, b_P)^T = (\mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{B})^{-1} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{d}, \quad (3)$$

Where $\mathbf{d} = (0,0, \dots, 0,1,0, \dots, 0,0)^T$ is the size of a column vector, $(2M+1,1)$, and \mathbf{A}^T is a matrix of dimensions, and $(P+1, 2M+1)$:

$$\mathbf{B}^T = \begin{pmatrix} (-N)^0 & \dots & (-1)^0 & 1 & 1^0 & \dots & N^0 \\ (-N)^1 & \dots & (-1)^1 & 0 & 1^1 & \dots & N^1 \\ (-N)^2 & \dots & (-1)^2 & 0 & 1^2 & \dots & N^2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ (-N)^P & \dots & (-1)^P & 0 & 1^P & \dots & N^P \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

When the size W and the degree O are held constant, it is clear that the values of the error coefficients rely solely on M and P and are insensitive to the input samples. Follow the formula in Eq(5) to get the correlation coefficient $r(U,V)$ (or $r(U,I)$) between the unaligned input U and the aligned input W (or I).

$$r(U, V) = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} [(u_n - \bar{u})(v_n - \bar{v})]}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (u_n - \bar{u})^2 \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (v_n - \bar{v})^2}},$$

$$r(U, I) = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} [(u_n - \bar{u})(i_n - \bar{l})]}{\sqrt{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (u_n - \bar{u})^2 \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (i_n - \bar{l})^2}},$$
(5)

where \bar{u}, \bar{v} and \bar{l} represents arithmetic mean of unaligned data and aligned data, respectively.

The first two procedures are repeated until convergence is achieved. At last, the sample points in each cluster are symbolically represented to produce the vector quantized data.

$$D = \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} \|y_i - v_j\|^2, j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k - 1$$
(6)

where y_i denotes the i^{th} sampling point, u_j denotes the j^{th} cluster center.

c. Feature extraction

In contrast to conventional feature selection algorithms, which use prediction performance as the primary criterion for selecting the features, the Boruta algorithm acts as a wrapper algorithm to guarantee that all features pertinent to the outcome variables are identified. The technique strongly emphasizes introducing more uncertainty within the feature set. The suggested technique determines the importance of features by randomly duplicating the original set and then combining the duplicate with the original to produce an extended feature set. Only features with greater value than the randomly selected traits will be considered important. Below is a detailed outline of the steps involved in the proposed method

i. Create randomized variants of every features (shadow features) and then combine them with the originals to form a larger collection of features.

ii. Using the larger set of characteristics, build a model, then analyze its importance using the average Z-score for lesser accuracy. Assuming the initial data is $y(d)$, we may create the upper and lower envelopes, $e_{\max}(d)$ and $e_{\min}(d)$, by using a cubic spline to interpolate between the local maxima and minima Z_{\max} provides the shadow feature's maximum Z value; the higher the value, the more important the feature.

iii. If a feature's Z score is greater than Z_{max} , at any point in the iteration, then that feature is retained. If not, we will judge the feature to be of low priority and delete it. As shown in Eq. (7), the mean envelope $m_1(d)$ obtained by averaging the upper and lower envelopes throughout time.

$$m_1(d) = \frac{1}{2} [e_{max}(d) + e_{min}(d)] \quad (7)$$

The mean envelope is subtracted from the raw signal data $x(t)$ to get the first component, $h_1(d)$, as stated in Eq. (8).

$$h_1(d) = x(d) - m_1(d) \quad (8)$$

Using Eq. (9), we can calculate the remaining dissimilar features $r_1(d)$ by subtracting $m_1(d)$ from the original features $x(d)$:

$$r_1(d) = x(d) - m_1(d) \quad (9)$$

iv. The algorithm achieves its maximum number of iterations, at which time the process is completed, or all features are either approved or rejected. With the recommended feature selection method, all essential traits are extracted, and the remainder is discarded.

d. Attack Prediction

There are three levels to the neural network model that is being presented. The activation function "relu" is used by 12 neurons in the input SDN layer. Eight neurons with an activation function of "relu" are employed in the model's inner hidden layer. The "Relu" function converts all negative input to zero and all positive input to positive ones. "sigmoid" is an output function found in the last layer of processing. This layer categorizes the results of the inner hidden layers into yes (1 for all) and no (0 for none) categories. Over fitting drastically affects the effectiveness of a machine learning algorithm; hence the architecture is built to prevent it. The gap between the two datasets, utilized as training and testing data, has been narrowed.

Each neuron takes in a large number of x-values (from 1 to n), and uses those values to calculate the expected z(i) output. As illustrated in equation (10), the characteristics of each neuron unit, w (weight vector) and b (bias), alter as a result of the learning process. The neuron computes its output at each iteration by multiplying " x " by weights and then adding bias. As illustrated in equation (11), the result is then generated by passing it through the nonlinear activation output. These weights are modified on a periodic basis based on an estimate of the deviation between actual and expected output:

$$Z = w_1 z_1 + w_2 z_2 + \dots + w_n z_n + b \quad (10)$$

We shall define the activation function as

$$\text{output } (D) = \text{activation } (w(D - 1) * x)y = g(Z), \quad (11)$$

where g is an activation function that has been used on the product of equation (11) and the original input.

The suggested neural network architecture links every neuron in one hidden layer to every neuron in the next hidden layer. It is crucial to go further into the nuances of how a certain output was made possible by a particular input. The total equation for generating layer-specific output may be summarized as follows:

$$\text{output} = \text{activation } (w(D - 1) * x) \quad (12)$$

The equation only applies to one layer in the recommended architecture since it also includes an additional hidden layer in addition to the input and output layers. The output of this layer (D) will be input for the next one, and the buried layer will do a similar calculation on this layer's output (D). As shown by equation (13), the binary cross-entropy loss function has been used as the loss function. It excels at anticipating the relationship between two binary output classes. As binary classification is involved, it is included into the recommended design.

$$H(q) = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N Z(i) \cdot \log(p(Z(i))) + (1 - Z(i)) \cdot \log(1 - p(Z(i))), \quad (13)$$

where y is the label (1 for the positive example of attack, 0 for the negative example of assault), and $p(y)$ is the estimated probability of the point being the positive example of attack for all N points. It uses less computing power, has a less impact on the environment, and excels at handling big problems with many variables.

IV. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

In this paper, we explain how we developed SDNNet- Binary Classifier, a prediction system to defend the SDN against UDP flood attacks. We build a deep-learning model using preexisting data to prevent such assaults. We use this prognosis to guide our choices on the SDN infrastructure. Many different metrics are in place to attempt to foretell network infiltration. Intrusion detection system features and efficacy are measured against a wide variety of metrics.

To evaluate the performance of the IDS, we compute its True Positive Rate (TPR) and False Positive Rate (FPR). Last but not least, we'll go through the measures like Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1 Score that were used to evaluate the performance of SDNNet-Binary Classifier. The study makes advantage of Python's simulation capabilities. We have tested the proposed approach for identifying the UDP attack using the data set to evaluate its viability and effectiveness.

Unnamed: 0	Protocol	Flow Duration	Total Fwd Packets	Total Backward Packets	Fwd Packets Length Total	Bwd Packets Length Total	Fwd Packet Length Max	Fwd Packet Length Min	Fwd Packet Length Mean	...	Active Mean	Active Std	Active Max	Active Min	Idle Mean	Idle Std	Idle Max	Idle Min	Lat	
0	0	17	216631	6	0	2088	0	393	321	348.0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	UT
1	1	17	2	2	0	802	0	401	401	401.0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	UT
2	2	17	48	2	0	766	0	383	383	383.0	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	UT
3	3	17	107319	4	0	1398	0	369	330	349.5	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	UT
4	4	17	107271	4	0	1438	0	389	330	359.5	...	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	UT

5 rows x 80 columns

Figure 2 Sample input

The sample input dataset attributes are illustrated in the figure 2

Figure 3 Types of attack

By implementing the novel SDN layer attack detection framework the attack type was predicted as depicted in the figure 3 and table 1

Table 1 Attack detection output

Class / Label	Attack
MSSQL	44
UDP	4654

The performance evaluation of the suggested methodology was done under certain parameters listed below,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Accuracy (A)} &= \frac{\text{Accurately classified records}}{\text{Total Samples}} * 100 \\
 \text{Precision (Pr)} &= \frac{\text{True Positive}}{\text{True Positive} + \text{False Positive}} * 100 \\
 \text{Recall (Rc)} &= \frac{\text{TruePositive}}{\text{TruePositive} + \text{FalseNegative}} * 100 \\
 \text{F1. measure} &= \frac{2.Rc.Pr}{Rc + Pr} * 100
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{14}$$

Figure 4 Performance analysis of SDNNet-Binary Classifier

As of from the result obtained the suggested methodology provide satisfied result by obtaining high range of Accuracy (99.8%), precision (100%), recall (100%), and F1 score (100%).

Figure 5 Comparative Performance Analysis

In order to prove the suggested framework’s efficiency, some of the existing framework implemented also compared with our methodology. As of from figure 5 the suggested methodology express satisfied prediction accuracy outcomes than other existing systems implemented. To prove the efficiency of the suggested methodology it can be compared with the existing mechanism

Table 2 Efficiency analysis of SDNNet–Binary Classifier

Paper	Accuracy	Pr.	Rc.	F1	Algorithm
Haider S et al. ³¹	99.45%	99.57	99.64	99.61	Ensemble CNN
Mousavi ³²	99.98%	99.03	99.04	99.50	Hybrid
Peng H et al. ³³	95.24%	N/A	N/A	N/A	SVM
Kottler S ³⁴	83.28%	96	72	82.82	RNN
Yin C et al. ³⁵	N/A	88.9	98.1	93.27	BiLSTM
SDNNet-Binary Classifier	99.8%	100	100	100	SDN layer attack detection framework

As of from the table 3 the proposed SDNNet-Binary Classifier outcomes was highly satisfied than some other mechanism which are recently in use.

V. CONCLUSION

An approach to predict UDP attacks from the provided dataset has been demonstrated in the paper. The suggested method for predicting software network layer attacks is one of the most accurate classification algorithms available today. It requires little in the way of feature preprocessing to get impressive results. The effectiveness of the proposed approach is reliant on the characteristics chosen with the help of the Iterative random wrapper Boruta algorithm. Additionally, it has obtained amazingly highly trustworthy findings in terms of accuracy. Future improvements may be made to the accuracy of categorization by applying other neural network models to the provided data set, such as adversarial neural networks and attention-based neural networks. Additionally, other types of attacks in SDN architecture may be included into the proposed model to enable remote monitoring of attack-related parameters during development of an efficient attack detection system.

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